

CARP Conference 2023

*Character Assassination, Illiberalism,
and the Erosion of Civic Rights*

Amsterdam
21-23 June 2023

Conference Programme & Practical Info

Character Assassination of Persian Patriot Development Reformists During Qajar Era: The Demise of Qaem-Maqam and Amir Kabir

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Panel 10 (Friday 23 June, 12.00am-1.15pm, University of Amsterdam Library, Belle van Zuylenzaal)

Abol-Qasem Qaem-Maqam Farahani (1779-1835) was the Grand Vizier (1834-1835) of Mohammad Shah Qajar; an influential figure during Fath Ali Shah's reign, he played a crucial role in securing Mohammad Shah's accession to the throne. He was a prominent prose-writer, and was known as a patriot and an incorruptible diplomatist. However, his strict policies prompted his rivals under the influence of British legations to persuade the King to remove him from office and order his execution. Under the aegis of Qaem Magham, Mirza Taghi Khan Farahani (1807-1852), known as Amir Kabir, commenced his government service, and later became the Grand Vizier (1848-1851) of Naser al-Din Shah Qajar. He is regarded as a reformer and pioneer of modernization in Iran; his numerous contributions include establishing Dar ul-Funun (polytechnic college) the first Western-style institute of higher education in Iran, substantial administrative and army reforms, combating corruption and bribery, and implementing independent foreign policy regarded as negative equilibrium by restricting Russian and British influences. Subsequently, his rivals through slanderous accusations induced the Shah to order his exile and ultimate execution. The strict policies of these two statesmen in the service of their country that threatened the political and economic interests of court officials, Britain, and Russia led to their systematic malicious defamation and demise. This study takes a historical phenomenological approach to provide an assessment of the lives of Qaem-Maqam and Amir Kabir, elaborates on their contributions, and accounts for interdependent variables which led to their downfalls.